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ABSTRACT

The present work deals with the production of cellulose nanoparticles through sonochemistry in various organic acidic media. The use of such organic acids represents low-environmental harm for the process. In contrast, the use of induced cavitation during chemical reaction balances the low effectiveness associated with the hydrolysis that uses organic acids, related to their low acidity. Overcoming the costs associated with extensive use of reagents and long reaction periods, which result in high-energy requirements, gives the value-added potential to an intrinsically green process. The selected organic acids were oxalic, maleic, and citric acid, chosen for their nature and their acid dissociation constant, as well as their availability in nature, which makes them green and cheap acidic media to produce cellulose nanocrystals. The acid concentration used was 0.2 moles for all the reactions; however, the pH, temperature, and reaction time were varied. The yields ranged between 20 and 40% depending on the reaction conditions, which are similar to typical cellulose nanocrystals yields. On the other hand, physicochemical analyses showed little differences between the different cellulose nanocrystals, thus indicating that the main benefit of having longer reaction times relies exclusively on the production yield. The resultant CNC surface contained carboxylic acid groups, which facilitate functionalization and dispersion in aqueous processing.

Sonochemical production of nanoscaled crystalline cellulose using organic acids

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The present work deals with the production of cellulose nanoparticles through sonochemistry in various organic acidic media. The use of such organic acids represents low-environmental harm for the process. In contrast, the use of induced cavitation during chemical reaction balances the low effectiveness associated with the hydrolysis that uses organic acids, related to their low acidity. Overcoming the costs associated with extensive use of reagents and long reaction periods, which result in high-energy requirements, gives the value-added potential to an intrinsically green process. The selected organic acids were oxalic, maleic, and citric acid, chosen for their nature and their acid dissociation constant, as well as their availability in nature, which makes them green and cheap acidic media to produce cellulose nanocrystals. The acid concentration used was 0.2 moles for all the reactions; however, the pH, temperature, and reaction time were varied. The yields ranged between 20 and 40% depending on the reaction conditions, which are similar to typical cellulose nanocrystals yields. On the other hand, physicochemical analyses showed little differences between the different cellulose nanocrystals, thus indicating that the main benefit of having longer reaction times relies exclusively on the production yield. The resultant CNC surface contained carboxylic acid groups, which facilitate functionalization and dispersion in aqueous processing.

INTRODUCTION

Cellulose nanocrystals (CNC), also known as cellulose whiskers, cellulose nanorods, or nanocrystalline cellulose, are renewable materials, which have high availability, are lightweight, and exhibit high mechanical properties. They consist of slender parallelepiped rods, and, depending on their origin, lateral dimensions ranging from about 2 - 50 nm in diameter, while lengths can be from 1 micrometer up to several tens of micrometers^{1,2}. They have been studied for their liquid crystalline behavior in concentrated aqueous suspensions^{3,4}, as well as for their reinforcing effect, when added to polymeric matrices, giving rise to robust and tough percolating networks of hydrogen-bonded structures^{5,6}. These materials are

prepared through acid hydrolysis, during which the amorphous sections of native cellulose are hydrolyzed, leaving a crystalline-enriched structure, which is then retrieved and neutralized through several methods. The most used way to obtain CNC consists of exposing cellulose to diluted inorganic acids, among which the most used have been hydrochloric acid (HCl) or sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄)^{7,8}. These reactions have been reported using different conditions (temperature, concentration, mixing speed, time). The dimensions and main physical properties of CNC depend on the source of the native cellulose, the acid employed, its concentration, and the hydrolysis conditions, mainly time and temperature. The hydrolysis process consists of removing the amorphous regions present in the cellulose fibrils leaving the crystalline regions intact; therefore, the dimensions of the cellulose obtained after hydrolysis are also dependent on the amount of amorphous regions in each native cellulose polymorph. Traditionally, the yields of CNC by acid hydrolysis have been quite low ($\approx 4\%$)⁶; however, recent studies have optimized the yields, reaching between 30 and 60 %^{9,10}.

The use of carboxylic acids for acid hydrolysis during the elaboration of CNC has been studied since the discovery of CNC, with carboxylic groups from dicarboxylic acids acting as claws hydrolyzing cellulose through the esterification of one carboxyl group^{11,12}. However, the weak character of such acids when compared to the more potent mineral acids has led to a virtual withdrawal of them. This has been influenced by processing conditions, which are not as efficient in terms of yield; moreover, other properties (such as the aspect ratio), being of considerable attention for CNC, are less competitive than CNC produced with mineral acids. Nevertheless, recent works have focused again on the use of such acids within the frame of greener chemistry for the production of CNC^{13–18}. These works have approached the use and recovery of different organic acids to produce CNC. The main problem they have faced is the high demand for time and temperature, but also the high amount of acids used to dampen the low dissociation constants that they have, compared to those of mineral acids. However, these conditions have achieved CNC that are morphologically similar to those of CNC produced with HCl and H₂SO₄ while having better physical properties as a result of partial esterification. Besides, they are sulfur-, and chlorine- free, and are obtained through greener processes, which are the main concerns regarding CNC, especially for applications involving biocompatibility. CNC have already revealed a significant number of potential uses, as can be touchscreens, capacitors, fuel cells, batteries, sensors, transparent conductive films, toxic material removal, and flexible electronics¹⁹. However, there are applications requiring desulfation of the surface of CNC after hydrolysis, a time-consuming and challenging process^{20,21}.

While the yields and properties of CNC obtained through carboxylic acid hydrolysis are so far motivating, there is still work to do regarding the process optimization, especially in terms of energy and time consumption. In this sense, the use of combined methods during the processing stands as a viable option to produce competitive CNC with full green technology. Among diverse approaches, the use of sonochemistry to synthesize nanomaterials has been studied extensively for many years^{11,22,23}. Nowadays, it is considered as one of the most powerful tools in the synthesis of nanostructured materials. Sonochemistry can be applied to engineer nanoscaled products, obtained from dry powder dispersed in aqueous media or to the re-dispersion of previously suspended nanoscaled materials²⁴.

The part of the sonic spectrum ranging from 20 kHz to 10 MHz is called ultrasound, and it can

be subdivided into three main regions: power ultrasound (20 - 100 kHz), high-frequency power ultrasound (100 kHz - 1 MHz) and diagnostic ultrasound (1 - 10 MHz)^{25,26}. The latter range is also often called high-frequency ultrasound²⁷. In the case of direct sonication, ultrasonic waves are generated in liquid suspensions by immersing an ultrasound probe into the suspension. Direct sonication yields a higher effective energy output into the suspension. Optimal sonication conditions are determined by assessing the effect of a variety of sonication parameters on the dispersion state of the suspension under a broad range of relevant conditions²⁸. Total effective acoustic energy to disrupt powder samples (clusters) is influenced by instrument and system-specific parameters. During sonication, the extreme local heating cycles in the bubble interface due to cavitation result in bulk heating of the liquid over time. This can lead to liquid evaporation or unintended chemical reactions in the suspension, leading to changes in the sonication volume and the sonochemical reaction, even provoking sample degradation²⁹. The avoidance of such heating can be achieved through simple batch systems (immersion of the sample in an ultrasonic bath) or more complex sonication systems that include refrigerated reactors or continuous flow sonication reactors. The total amount of energy (E) delivered to a system depends on two operational factors: acoustic power (P) and residence time (t), related through the equation $E = P \times t$. Therefore, the elapsed time at which a sample is prepared plays a crucial role in consolidating the suspension²⁵.

The use of higher concentrations increases the particle collision frequency, enhances the particle disruption because of the increased particle-particle collision probability, but also generates higher kinetic energy, which implies faster sample heating. On the other hand, the increase in particle collisions can lead to aggregation or coalescence of particles. The preparation of nanoparticle dispersion in liquid media by the application of ultrasonic energy has been used widely in the disruption of lignocellulosic biomass either as a catalyst in a reaction or as part of sequential treatment, involving chemical and physical disruption of lignocelluloses³⁰⁻³². However, its use in the synthesis of cellulose nanoparticles has been mostly relegated to re-dispersion of previously hydrolyzed CNC (mostly with inorganic acids) or as reaction media *via* indirect sonication.

In this work, sonochemical reactions using three different organic acids were used to hydrolyze cellulose into cellulose nanocrystals as greener and more efficient alternative to manufacture such products. The influence of direct sonication as an intensifier for the hydrolysis reaction was studied by using low acid concentrations compared to those of literature, as well as using mild reaction conditions, *i.e.*, lower temperature and processing time.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 summarizes the reaction conditions for each experiment. The selection of a direct sonication to boost hydrolysis was kept at low times to avoid or reduce any corruptions from either the acidic media^{33,34} or the cavitation itself³⁵. For this reason, most of the reaction was done with an indirect sonication, which has proved its efficiency in reducing time while increasing the yield during acid hydrolysis³⁶⁻³⁸. Direct sonication was done by immersing a 13 mm uniform horn directly into the media (30 mm from the bottom of the flask). In contrast, indirect sonication was done by immersing the reaction flask inside an ultrasonic bath at 30

mm from the transducer sandwich (located at the bottom). The average energy delivered to the system was 48.46 ± 9.58 kJ for direct sonication time (DST) of 10 min. In comparison, for DST of 15 min, the energy delivered to the system averaged 58.64 ± 4.62 kJ as measured by the equipment. In the case of indirect sonication time (IST), the delivered energy was calculated with the calorimetric method, resulting in 62.56 ± 0.33 kJ for samples with IST of 120 min, and 62.90 ± 0.15 kJ for samples with IST of 150 min.

Table 1. Reaction conditions for each selected experiment

Sample	Acid	DST ^a [min]	IST ^b [min]	RT ^c [°C]
C1	Citric	10	120	60
C2	Citric	10	150	60
C3	Citric	15	120	60
M1	Maleic	10	120	60
M2	Maleic	10	150	60
M3	Maleic	15	120	60
O1	Oxalic	10	120	60
O2	Oxalic	10	150	60
O3	Oxalic	15	120	60
S1	Sulfuric	—	90	60

^aDirect sonication time

^bIndirect sonication time

^cReaction temperature

Yields as a function of direct and indirect sonication time are presented in Fig. 1 and 2. Two different yields were assessed, the first one corresponds to the amount of matter passing through a 40 μm coarse sintered glass plate, containing both micro and nanoscale cellulose particles, and the second one corresponding to the smallest fraction. Fig. 1 presents the yields of the first fraction, which was used to compare the influence of direct sonication on the hydrolysis of cellulose. The contour images clearly show trends proving that the use of direct sonication has a positive effect on the hydrolysis, with two different directions shown. While for oxalic acid, the use of direct sonication has a catalytic impact during acid hydrolysis, for maleic acid and citric acid, the hydrolysis was also influenced by the duration of the indirect sonication. This can be related to the lower acid dissociation constant of oxalic acid (1.7), compared to maleic (1.9) and citric (3.128) acids. On the other hand, the contour lines show that maleic acid yielding depends directly proportional on both direct and indirect sonication time. In contrast, citric acid seems to depend more on indirect sonication rather than the direct one. Fig. 2 displays graphics that present the yield of the second fraction (nanocellulose) as a surface response related to the direct and indirect sonication time. Fig. S1[†] shows further information to understand the influence of direct sonication time, indirect sonication time, and the accumulated amount of energy delivered to the probe in the yields. The acid with the highest yield was in general oxalic acid, having reached almost 17% for O2 and O3, while M2 and M3 ranged between 13 and 14%, regarding citric acid, C2, and C3 had similar values.

However, for shorter reaction times, the yields were much lower, O1 having yields around 12–13%, while for M1 was between 7 and 10% and for citric acid between 5 and 8%. These values reveal the importance of longer times for the carboxylic acids to disrupt cellulose fibers properly. Moreover, in Fig. S1,[†] the energy dependence of the reaction can be appreciated. Cellulose dispersions being a heterogeneous solution, having a homogeneous distribution of cavitation bubbles at higher concentrations, is difficult to achieve; thus, it is affecting the interaction between the probe and the media.

Fig. 1 Yields of the first recovered cellulose fraction as a function of direct and indirect sonication.

Fig. 2 Obtained yields related to direct sonication time, indirect sonication time, and energy

This generated that the energy varied even within the same sample. While in general, time and energy had a direct relation and most reactions at 10 min delivered between 30 and 50 kJ, in some experiments, the energy reached higher values. This happened in particular for maleic acid. Generally, the obtained yields are rather high compared with typical organic acid hydrolyzes, which have ranged between 3 and 25% with prolonged reaction times and high temperatures^{14,17,39}. However, the yields are still low when compared with reactions catalyzed with HCl, in which yields have reached 85 %¹⁶. More recent works have also included a ball milling step before acid hydrolysis aiming to avoid the use of HCl. In those works, they have achieved a yield of 25% with maleic anhydride⁴⁰ and up to 65 % with citric acid⁴¹. However, reaction times and acid concentration are still high. In this sense, the obtaining of nanocellulose through sonochemical reactions with organic acids has resulted in a successful intensification method to achieve competitive yields of nanocelluloses, considering that during indirect sonication, the difference between the delivered energy is rather low.

Fig. 3 presents the FT-IR spectra of the different nanocelluloses obtained through hydrolysis with citric, maleic, oxalic, and sulfuric acids under different reaction conditions, as well as the reference cellulose. The spectra of the obtained nanocelluloses maintain a similar shape with the spectrum of the microcrystalline cellulose. In the region between the 3700–2700 cm^{-1} , one can see the presence of a broad band assigned to –OH stretching vibration, which is an

envelope of the bands belonging to different hydrogen bonding stretching vibrations. At the same time, the presence of the various stretching and bending vibration of the cellulose groups, as well as the presence of the esterification of the cellulose, is observed in the fingerprint region. To better highlight the individual bands, the second derivative spectra were performed (Fig. 4), and the bands position and their assignments are listed in Tables S1 and S2 (ESI†). The assignment of the characteristic bands was made according to literature data^{42–45}.

Fig. 3 Infrared spectra of the MCC and the obtained nanocelluloses.

From Fig. 4, one can observe the presence of the specific bands assigned to all types of H-bonds present in cellulose structure, with more definite differences occurring for the bands from 3345 and 3276 cm^{-1} assigned to O(3)H \cdots O(5) intramolecular hydrogen bonds in cellulose and O(6)H \cdots O(3) intermolecular hydrogen bonds in cellulose monoclinic phase I β ^{42,44–48}. These bands are more intense in the spectra of hydrolyzed nanocelluloses with the organic acids, comparing to those from cellulose and CNC processed with sulfuric acid and are shifted to higher wavenumber values comparing to MCC. This indicates higher variations of the O(3)H \cdots O(5) intra and O(6)H \cdots O(3) intermolecular hydrogen bonds.

In the fingerprint region (1850–400 cm^{-1}) (Fig. 3 and 4), higher differences for the samples treated with organic acids were observed by the formation of new bands at about 1806, 1743, 1673, 1640 and 1570 cm^{-1} , assigned to C=O bonds in carbonyl, ester and acetyl groups, conjugated acids, as well as carboxylate ($-\text{COO}^-$) groups. All these bands are due to the interaction of the organic acids with cellulose and do not present high intensities, suggesting a moderate degree of esterification.

Other significant changes are observed for the bands from 1643, 1460, 989, 895, and 812 cm^{-1}

with a decrease in intensity after processing. They are assigned to stretching vibration of adsorbed water molecules, C–H deformation vibration, C–O stretching vibration, and β -glucosidic linkage between the sugar units in hemicelluloses and celluloses stretching vibration, respectively.

At the same time, the bands from about 1165, 1115, 1063, and 1025 cm^{-1} increase in intensity after the processing. They are assigned to C–O–C stretching vibration, glucose ring stretching vibration, C–O stretching vibration mainly from C(3)–O(3)H, and C–O stretching ring vibration, respectively. The band from 1165 cm^{-1} is assigned to crystalline regions in cellulose. Therefore, the intensity increase of this band is mainly due to an increase in the crystallinity of the samples after the organic acid processing, but also to the presence of the C–O groups from esters. The maxima vary according to treatment conditions, as well as the type of acid used (see Table S2+).

Fig. 4 Second derivative infrared spectra in the 3700–2700 cm^{-1} and 1850–700 cm^{-1} regions of the MCC and obtained nanocelluloses.

The UV–Vis absorbance of the different nanocelluloses, either as a 1 wt% suspensions or a 140 μm film, can be seen in Fig. 5. It can be observed that there is a higher UV absorbance in all the nanocelluloses made with carboxylic acids than in those made with sulfuric acid, with lower transmittance in case of citric (tricarboxylic) acid than those of oxalic and maleic (dicarboxylic) acids. This is related to the absorbance of carboxylic acids ranging between 180 and 300 nm and to hydrogen bonds occurring near the CvO groups.^{49,50} This high UV absorbance has an

important potential as a protective additive, either in food packaging or in the cosmetic industry.⁵¹

Fig. 5 UV-Vis spectra of the manufactured nanocelluloses.

Films had, in general, higher transmittance than the one elaborated with sulfuric acid, except for nanocelluloses made with citric acid, which had lower transmittance in the UV-Vis spectra. Transmittance at 550 nm, present in the inset of Fig. 5 shows how there is a higher light transmittance in the case of maleic acid samples, followed by oxalic acid samples, while the least transmittance was observed for citric acid samples. Transmittance at 550 nm is related to the nanocellulose dimensions, surface area, and interactions as a reduced air/solid interface allowing a higher light transmittance due to a reduction in the refractive index.⁵²

Fig. 6 presents the XRD powder diffraction patterns. These patterns were used to calculate the d_{hkl} spaces, the linear crystallite size proposed by Scherrer, and the crystallinity index (X_c), which are displayed in Fig. 7. It is perceptible that the slight signal present at 2θ 21.067 and that corresponds to a small contribution of the -110 crystalline plane of anorthic cellulose α . In general, all the hydrolyzed celluloses present three main signals associated with the $1-10$, 110 , and 200 crystalline domains of monoclinic cellulose β , with the contribution of the signal associated with the 004 crystalline planes being drastically reduced for all the celluloses hydrolyzed with organic acids.

Fig. 6 XRD powder diffraction patterns of the different nanocelluloses.

The d_{hkl} spacing of the samples did not present any significant change (Fig. 7), thus meaning that the arrangement of the crystalline planes is not affected. However, crystallite domains (L) and the fraction of cellulose chains contained in the interiors of crystallites (X) do present differences between samples. L is inversely proportional to the integral breadth of the diffraction signal, which means that narrower signals in the diffractogram result in larger crystallite domains. In addition, the increase in the crystallite domains and the crystallite interior chain content are directly proportional to the crystallinity of the cellulose as a result of a decrease in the chain mobility.⁵³

Fig. 7 d_{hkl} spacing, linear crystallite domain, and crystallite interior chain of the different nanocelluloses.

Fig. 8 shows the NMR spectra of the elaborated nanocelluloses. As can be seen, there are no significant changes in the structure of ^{13}C CP/MAS spectra. The main differences are appreciated in the C4 region, which is related to the crystallinity of cellulose,⁵⁴ and which was used to calculate values presented in Fig. 9. The C6 region shows a broad shift, whose broadening after hydrolysis is related to mild esterification occurring in the C6 position.¹⁴ However, chemical shifts related to oxalate, maleate, and citrate were not perceptible, as the esterification was in general low.

Fig. 8 ^{13}C CP/MAS NMR chemical shifts of the different nanocelluloses.

Fig. 9 presents the crystallinity indices calculated by different methods. The first one corresponds to the Hermans crystallinity index, which is the most reliable value that can be obtained from diffraction patterns as it considers the fitted signals associated to each crystalline domain, the second corresponds to the Segal index, which is the most commonly used and can be compared qualitatively with most of the values analyzed in the bibliography. While it has been long withdrawn as a legitimate value, it is still widely used. The other two methods correspond to the integrated areas of C4 and C6 carbons obtained from NMR spectra, which attribute a crystalline and an amorphous domain for each of those carbons⁵⁴. By applying a regression curve to each of the obtained values, the R^2 obtained is 0.954 for C4,

0.836 for H, 0.716 for C6, and 0.659 for S. $Z < 0$ indicates that $I\beta$ is the pre-dominant form.⁵⁵ Z values reflect a predominance of monoclinic cellulose $I\beta$, and this was incremented with the extended hydrolysis conditions, which has been associated with a partial conversion of cellulose $I\alpha$ into cellulose $I\beta$ during the sonochemical hydrolysis.⁵⁶

Fig. 9 Crystallinity indices and Z values of the different nanocelluloses. H indicates Hermans, S indicates Segal; C4 and C6 indicate NMR C4 and C6 integration, respectively.

Fig. 10 presents selected $5 \mu\text{m} \times 5 \mu\text{m}$ topographies (top view, height mode) of the elaborated nanocelluloses, morphologies are similar to other works that used organic acids to hydrolyze cellulose^{13,18} in which refers to the neck stretching presented by the fibrils. This is not seen in mineral acid nanocrystals, as seen in literature or the control sample (S1, Fig. S3[†]), in which there is an evident detachment of the CNC between each other. This is undoubtedly related to the weakness of the organic acids, but also the low temperature of the reactions. Nonetheless, this partial trimming or narrowing is not present in traditional cellulose nanofibers or similar materials, in which fibers are defibrillated mechanically and preserve the fibril morphology without having any steepness. Fig. S4 to S12[†] present two-tone images of various AFM micro-graphics for each sample. These images allow observing more clearly the narrowing of the fibers at the amorphous sections, with different zones found for each sample. From these images, it is possible to assess the efficiency of hydrolyses, with M1, M2, and O3 presenting shapes closer to traditional CNC, while C1 has a morphology more similar to CNF. These results are concurrent with viscosities, shown in Fig. 11, as particles with a higher aspect ratio need higher shear to assemble. Fig. S13 to S18[†] present detailed information about sizes as measured from AFM topographies.

Fig. 10 AFM micrographs of the different nanocelluloses.

Two different methods were selected to measure cellulose nanoparticles from AFM. The first consisted in the built-in function to analyze particles, which allows measuring faster a larger number of particles, in this case, the diameter (or length) and the height of the particle are measured with boundaries set at the threshold height (Fig. S13[†]), the second consisted in manually measuring the length and width of the nanoparticles (Fig. S16[†]). From these measurements, 2D kernel density plots were elaborated (Fig. S14 and S17[†]) as well as box charts using the 25%–75% quartile interval and marking the minimum and maximum ranges and the mean values (Fig. S15 and S18[†]). From these values, two main things can be assessed, the absolute values from the samples, in which the smallest nanoparticle can be considered as the best, but also the homogeneity of the sample, which means that the process is more robust. In this sense, both in width and height, M3 was the most homogeneous sample, meaning that nanoparticles made with maleic acid with longer direct sonication had a consistent cross-section; for the rest of the samples, there was no direct relation between width and height in terms of homogeneity. In terms of mean values, samples made with maleic acid were in general larger and thicker, with C1 and O2 having the smaller particles in the hand-measured distribution, and C1 and O3 in the computer-aided measurement. One way ANOVA with Tukey test at a 0.05 significance level was used to evaluate the mean values. Statistical analysis showed that for the manually measured nanoparticles, the only significant differences were of O1 with O2 and O3. At the same time, for computer-aided measurements there were significant differences between the samples made with 15 min of direct sonication (C3, M3,

and O3) and the others, thus showing that the use of a longer direct sonication had a positive effect in the length of samples made with maleic and oxalic acids. In terms of cross-section measurements, there was a consistent significant difference between C1 and O2, with the nanoparticles elaborate with the same acid, which means that C1 had the average smallest cross-section from all the samples (mean values: 17.82 nm height and 41.62 nm width).

Fig. 11 shows the viscosity related to shear rate curves for the different nanocelluloses at a 0.1% concentration on a logarithmic scale. At high shear rates, the structure of the nanocellulose suspension reorganizes into the chiral nematic phase due to flow, and this gives a low viscosity state^{21,57}. In general, samples did not present a significant Newtonian plateau. However, there were perceptible differences between the observed shear thinning. C1, M2, and O2 showed less acute shear thinning, meaning that the ordering of the anisotropic nanocellulose suspensions had a weaker thinning zone, typical of large-chain polymeric solutions.

Fig. 11 Viscosity versus shear rate for nanocellulose suspensions with a concentration of 0.1 wt%.

In Fig. 12, the thermogravimetric analysis plots and first derivative plots are presented. In Fig. S13,† it can be found the transition temperatures and the char residue at 600 °C. Thermograms showed increased thermal stability with a lower residue as compared to CNC made with sulfuric acid; most of the samples had a char content below 5%, with M3 having an almost null content of char. It was found that there was an increased onset temperature in all citric acid samples. O1 and M3 presented the temperature for the maximum decomposition rate at ≈ 350 °C, which was lower than that of cellulose (356 °C), while for S1 was at 320 °C. These results are concurrent with previously reported data,¹⁵ in which there is an increase in the thermal stability of CNC made with carboxylic acids. Moreover, while for S1, the mass loss at 100 °C is around 4%, the nanocelluloses elaborated with carboxylic acids had losses below 1%, implying a low moisture uptake. Regarding the char residue after

carbonization, Fig. S14† presents correlation analysis of residue at 600 °C and D.P. and COOH content. From these results, it can be seen that there are positive correlations (Pearson >0). However, both correlations were not significant at the 0.05 level. Nonetheless, it can be appreciated that the main relation is built with the D. P., thus marking that the carboxylation was weak. The increase of the starting temperature for thermal decomposition is higher in S1, as sulfate groups accelerated decay, S1 also had higher residue at 600 °C, with most elaborated nanocelluloses having low residue, this can be related with a high surface area.¹⁶

Fig. 12 TG and dTG thermograms of the elaborated nanocelluloses.

The degree of substitution and COOH content as obtained from conductometric titration are considerably lower than other works (Table 2). The highest value was observed for O2, followed by M2 and O3, while the lowest values were recorded for C1, M3, and M1. In general, there is a common trend in which D.S. is higher in samples having an indirect sonication of 150 min; moreover, samples sonicated indirectly for 120 min had higher D.S. when sonicated directly 10 min than those being sonicated directly for 10 min, thus being constant the 2 > 3 > 1 tendency disregarding the acid employed. On the other hand, the highest D.S. was achieved with oxalic acid, while the lowest was with citric acid. The difference between the obtained results and thus reported by previous works, in which D.S. reached values between 0.1 and 0.2,^{14,16,18} can be related to the reaction time and temperature. While in the present work, the highest D.S. was obtained at the longest reaction times, the low temperature compared to other studies may have influenced the COOH-cellulose reactivity.

Table 2 Conductometric degree of substitution, carboxylic content, degree of polymerization, and molecular weight of the different nanocelluloses.

Sample	CDS ^a	COOH [mmol g ⁻¹]	DP ^b	M _w ^c [g mol ⁻¹]
C1	0.052	0.908	1022	165 757
C2	0.073	0.878	755	122 476
C3	0.066	0.879	1679	272 196
M1	0.058	0.82	1350	218 818
M2	0.076	0.747	1131	183 453
M3	0.055	0.716	651	105 608
O1	0.067	0.824	1037	168 146
O2	0.076	0.911	915	148 415
O3	0.073	0.692	742	120 233

^a Conductometric degree of substitution. ^b Degree of polymerization. ^c Molecular weight.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Microcrystalline cellulose (CAS 9004-34-6, average particle size 90 μm), oxalic acid (CAS 144-62-7), citric acid (CAS 77-92-9) and maleic acid (CAS 110-16-7) were purchased from Acros Organics, while sulfuric acid (CAS: 7664-93-9) was purchased from Fischer Chemicals.

For each sample, 5 g of microcrystalline cellulose was dried for 24 h at 50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and then kept inside a conditioning chamber with no humidity at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Three different solutions were prepared with a 0.2 $\text{mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ concentration: oxalic acid (1.46 wt%, pH 0.82), maleic acid (4 wt%, pH 1.65) and citric acid (2.2 wt%, pH 1.10). All hydrolyses were made with a 1 : 10 solid to liquid ratio, in twin-neck round-bottom flasks to control the reaction temperature. As a control, CNC were made following the method described previously using a 10.2 M sulfuric acid solution and performing the reaction at 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ during 60 min⁵⁸.

Sonochemical hydrolysis

Sonochemical reactions were made inside an Elma S70H (effective power 150 W, power density 34.88 $\text{W}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) ultrasonic bath, Elmasonic (Germany) with three piezoelectric sandwich transducer systems working with a frequency of 37 kHz and internally controlled heating (600 W). The temperature was controlled both by the system and by regulating the inlet–outlet of water when independent thermocouples indicated overheating of the reaction temperature. Reactions were stopped with cold distilled water (1 : 3 v/v). The non-hydrolyzed fraction was separated with a Buchner funnel with a sintered disc filter funnel (pore size <40 μm). The hydrolysate was washed three times by using a nylon membrane (0.22 μm), and then CNC were corrected to a 3 wt% concentration and sonicated directly for 3 min at 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ with power set at 80 W.⁵⁹

Reaction time and temperature were set with a lean design, in which temperatures were ranged between 45 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 70 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and reaction times were varied between 60 and 240 min (results not shown). The effectiveness was measured as the ratio between the retained solid matter in a <40 μm sintered glass funnel and the filtrate. The selected times correspond to the range, with at least 90 % of the reacted samples passed through a coarse glass filter. With these least acceptable results, the temperature was set at 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, while two reaction times were selected, being 120 and 150 min. These conditions are similar to other studies that have proved the effectiveness of using sonochemically-assisted hydrolysis of cellulose.^{11,28}

A pre-hydrolysis was made *via* direct sonication to optimize the yield and promote a process intensification. The sono-chemical system selected for the first step for cellulose disruption consisted of a Sonopuls S3200 Ultrasonic homogenizer (200 W), Bandelin (Germany) with an ultrasonic transducer AMPLICHRON® for constant amplitude. This means that sample viscosity did not affect the amplitude, the transducer was connected to a lead zirconate-titanate (PZT) ultrasonic oscillating system, which was coupled to a titanium alloy booster-horn ending in a titanium alloy flat tip (13 mm) with direct probe contact. The probe was immersed 15 mm in any sample; frequency was continuously delivered by the high-frequency generator at 20 kHz \pm 500 Hz. All samples were elaborated under continuous sound (no pulsation), and amplitude was set at 170 μm_{ss} (100%). Reactions were done for 10 or 15 min, placing the flasks inside a water-cooling bath, with a process block set, if the temperature

reached the final reaction temperature for the upcoming step (60 °C).

Yields

The yields were calculated by measuring the recovered hydrolyzed and non-hydrolyzed fractions gravimetrically:

$$Y = M_R \cdot M_0^{-1}$$

where M_R is the recovered mass (dry weight) of cellulose, and M_0 is the cellulose mass before hydrolysis.

Three different fractions were selected: the first corresponded to the mass passing through a 40 μm pore and being retained by a 16 μm pore; the second consisted of the mass passing the 16 μm pore and being retained by a 0.22 μm nylon membrane; the final fraction consisted of the particles separated from the second fraction through continuous centrifugation at 8000 rpm until the supernatant was turbid.

Nanocellulose characterization

Particle morphology and surface topographies were analyzed *via* atomic force microscopy (AFM) with a Multimode TM-AFM with a NanoScope IIIa controller, Digital instruments Inc. (USA), Veeco Instruments Inc. (USA), Bruker (Germany). A Cu tip was used in tapping mode. Samples were prepared by spin coating a Muscovite mica disc with a $\approx 10 \mu\text{l}$ drop ($\approx 0.001\%$ CNC suspension). Images were processed with Nanoscope Analysis 1.9 software (Bruker).

X-ray powder diffraction patterns were collected with a Panalytical Phillips X'Pert PRO multipurpose diffractometer, with samples mounted on a zero background silicon wafer fixed in a generic sample holder, using monochromatic $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$) in a 2θ range from 5 to 40° with a step size of 0.026° and 80 s per step of at room temperature.

The ^{13}C CP-MAS NMR spectrometry was performed using a Bruker 500 MHz spectrometer at a frequency of 250 MHz with an acquisition time of 0.011 s at room temperature.

Infrared spectra were recorded on a Bruker ALPHA FT-IR spectrometer in transmission mode in KBr pellets, in the wave-length range from 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} , with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} , and 32 scans. The concentration in the pellets was 2 mg sample per each 200 mg KBr. The processing of the spectra was done in Grams 9.1 program (Thermo Fisher Scientific).

Shear viscosity was measured using a viscometer Alfa (Fungilab) with a small sample adapter (APM/B), and a TL5 spindle. Samples containing 0.1% of cellulose were measured at different shear rates. For cellulose degree of polymerization, samples were first dispersed to form a 1 wt% water suspension and then solubilized (1 : 1) with 1 M cupriethylenediamine solution and measured using a capillarity viscometer.⁶⁰ Cellulose degree of polymerization was calculated from the intrinsic viscosity using the Staudinger–Mark–Houwink equation.⁶¹

Conductometric titration was used to measure the carboxyl group content. For this, 10 mL of a 1 wt% dispersion of each nanocellulose sample was prepared (Type II water). Samples were stabilized in their conductance between 100 and 200 mSm^{-1} measured using a Cond 8 (X.S. instruments) conductance meter by using a 10 mmol L^{-1} NaCl solution. The conductance was continually recorded while adding a NaOH solution of 10 mmol L^{-1} dropwise until the second inflection was observed. The NaOH volume recorded at the second inflection point was used to calculate the carboxyl group content *via* the following expression:

$$\text{Carboxyl content} = C \cdot V \cdot m^{-1}$$

where C and V are the molarity (mol L^{-1}) and consumed volume (L) of the NaOH solution, respectively; m is the mass in g of cellulosic sample.^{62,63}

The UV–Vis light transmittance spectra of CNC suspensions (1 wt%) and films (thickness $140 \pm 30 \mu\text{m}$) were measured in a wavelength range of 200–1000 nm using Jasco V-630 spectrophotometer.^{13,52}

Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) was carried out in a TGA Q2500 calorimeter from T.A., with a heating ramp of $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$, from 30 to $600 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in a controlled atmosphere of N_2 .

CONCLUSIONS

Nanocelluloses were elaborated sonochemically using organic acids as reaction media, which constituted a green and effective method. Yields were similar to those reported in previous works using organic acids to hydrolyze cellulose, while the reaction temperature and time were drastically reduced, thus confirming an intensification process. The morphologies of the elaborated nanocelluloses were similar to previous work, resulting in a hybrid between cellulose nanofibers and cellulose nanocrystals, with narrowing sections through the length of the fibers. This influenced the rheological behavior of the nanocelluloses in suspension, as the self-assembly of the chiral nematic cellulose depended on their morphology. The use of organic acids resulted in mild esterifications, as observed by FTIR spectroscopy, as well as conductometric titration. This influenced the UV absorbance of the nanocelluloses, characteristic which may be useful for packaging and biomedical applications. The obtained nanocelluloses also presented higher thermal stability than those elaborated with sulfuric acid, property important for potential applications for the coating industry. The results show that the most effective reaction to hydrolyze cellulose into nanoparticles was oxalic acid with 15 min direct sonication time, which is related to its lower dissociation constant. On the other hand, the reactions conducted during longer periods resulted in a higher degree of substitution and carboxyl content, in particular noticeable for oxalic acid and maleic acid.

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